

SHORT NOTES

Reaction of Grignard Reagents with Heterocyclic Compounds

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Bergstrom and McAllister (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2845) obtained 2-alkyl- or 2 aryl-pyridines or quinolines by the action of ethyl- or phenylmagnesium bromide on pyridine or quinoline. Goetz-Luthy (*ibid.*, 1949, **71**, 2254) failed, however, to isolate any 2-ethylpyridine and found that ethylmagnesium bromide with pyridine gave, presumably, a small quantity of dipyrindyl, but most of the pyridine was recovered unchanged.

The action of the Grignard reagents on the 2-, 3-, or 4- picoline and quinaldine does not appear to have been reported, although the activity of the hydrogen atoms of the methyl group is well known. Thus Levine *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1951, **73**, 4301) found that 2-picoline was converted to its lithium derivative by the action of phenyllithium. It has now been found that addition of ethereal solutions of 2-, 3-, or 4- picoline or quinaldine to a solution of phenylmagnesium bromide (in ether) results in the formation of a white precipitate. This immediately dissolves in all cases except in the case of 4-picoline. The colour of the solution turns red in all cases. The reaction with pyridine also gave an insoluble white precipitate but not with quinoline. In the latter case, the ethereal solution deposited colorless cubic crystals on cooling. This is quite different from that reported by Gilman (*ibid.*, 1949, **71**, 2327).

The precipitates were obtained in nearly quantitative yield. That from 4-picoline appeared to be more stable than the one from pyridine, but both decomposed when left exposed to air. In a desiccator these did not decompose. The precipitates reacted vigorously with water leaving a small residue and the original heterocyclic compound. The cubic crystals behaved in a similar manner. None of these had any definite melting point, but these melted over a wide range of temperature. The nature of these complexes is being investigated.

Among the reaction products diphenyl was identified. The quantity of this product varied in each case, but was always less than that expected. This was verified by refluxing an ethereal solution of phenylmagnesium bromide under the same conditions as that under which the reactions were carried out. A preliminary investigation of the reaction products revealed that substitution in the side chain of the heterocyclic compounds did not occur. Only in the case of 2-picoline, a small quantity (3%) of a base was obtained which reacted with methyl iodide to afford a substance quite different from 2-picoline methiodide (chars at $> 200^{\circ}$ and m.p. 250°).

Gilman (*ibid.*, 1957, **79**, 1245; 1959, **81**, 4000) has reported the reaction between allylmagnesium bromide and some heterocyclic compounds. The action of this reagent on picolines and 4-methylcinnoline has now been studied. It appears that the reaction took place in all cases where the 2-position was free. Thus 2-picoline and 2,6-lutidine do not appear to react. White or yellowish precipitates, similar to those described above, were also obtained. Further work is in progress and will be reported in another communication.